

Mass Spectral Fragmentation Patterns of Some Substituted 1,2,4-Triazoles and 1,2,4-Triazolo[3,4-*b*]1,3,4-thiadiazoles^ψ

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Several substituted 1,2,4-triazoles (**1**) have been synthesized and converted into 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**3**). They have been characterized by ir, nmr and mass spectral studies. The mass spectral fragmentation patterns of the compounds are described.

Triazoles and their fused derivatives¹ are known for their antibacterial, fungicidal and pesticidal properties², while 1,3,4-thiadiazoles are associated with various biological activities³. Keeping these in view, 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**3**) were synthesized starting from substituted 1,2,4-triazoles (**1**) by employing a 30% solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid. As a part of structural investigation, mass spectra of five Schiff bases (**1a-e**) and six cyclized products (**3a-f**) were recorded.

The mass spectral decomposition modes of various triazolothiadiazoles and Schiff bases containing arylfuran substituents have been investigated.

Scheme 1, Mass fragmentation pattern of the Schiff bases.

Scheme 2. Mass fragmentation pattern of triazolothiadiazoles (3a-f).

Results and Discussion

All the spectra showed characteristic common fragmentation pathways with intense molecular ion peaks in most cases. The molecular ions of **1a** and **1b** underwent fragmentations to produce peaks at m/z 214, corresponding to the molecular ion of *p*-nitrophenylfuronitrile. It further underwent loss of NO and CO to give peaks at m/z 184 and 156 respectively, which is a characteristic fragmentation pattern of nitrophenylfuran derivatives⁴. A peak at m/z 203 as the base peak, found in the MS of **1c**, corresponds to the *o*-chlorophenylfuronitrile ion. The molecular ions of the Schiff bases **1a-c** were also found to undergo fragmentations to produce ions of triazoles at m/z 115, 129 and 211/213, respectively (Scheme 1).

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TABLE 1—MASS FRAGMENTATION DATA OF 1a-e

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	m/z (% Abundance)					
			M ⁺	A	B	C	D	E
1a	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	CH ₃	329 (27)	214 (14)	115 (95)	140 (34)	160 (28)	168 (18)
b	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₂ H ₅	343 (39)	214 (17)	129 (100)	140 (20)	160 (33)	168 (5)
c	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂ H ₅	332/334 (22)	203/205 (100)	129 (23)	140 (46)	149/151 (51)	168 (4)
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	CH ₃	329 (15)	214 (100)	115 (8)	140 (5)	160 (1)	168 (3)
e	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	458/460 (10)	247/249 (100)	211/213 (70)	140 (60)	193/195 (10)	168 (5)

The arylfuronitriles **A** (from **1a** and **1c**) were found to undergo characteristic fragmentation pattern. The loss of CO and CN radical from these species resulted in the formation of arylpropenyl cations at *m/z* 160 and 149/151 respectively. The loss of Cl and NO₂ radicals from the arylfuronitriles gave a common ion peak at *m/z* 168. Subsequent loss of CO from this ion (*m/z* 168) resulted in another common ion peak at *m/z* 140.

TABLE 2—MASS FRAGMENTATION DATA OF 3a-f

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	m/z (% Abundance)			
			M ⁺	F	G	H
3a	<i>o</i> -Cl	CH ₃	316/318 (10)	221/223 (3)	177/179 (-)	149/151 (85)
b	<i>p</i> -Cl	CH ₃	316/318 (20)	221/223 (10)	177/179 (-)	149/151 (10)
c	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	CH ₃	327 (46)	232 (1)	188 (7)	160 (8)
d	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₂ H ₅	341 (29)	232 (-)	188 (7)	160 (7)
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₂ H ₅	341 (5)	232 (5)	188 (1)	160 (10)
f	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₃ H ₇	355 (44)	232 (-)	188 (3)	160 (4)

The mass spectra of the triazolothiadiazoles **3a**, **b**, **c** and **e** showed intense molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 327, 341, 355 and 316/318, consistent with the molecular formulae

C₁₄H₉N₅O₃S, C₁₅H₁₁N₅O₃S, C₁₆H₁₃N₅O₃S and C₁₄H₉ClN₄OS respectively. These molecular ions underwent fragmentations to give ions at *m/z* 232 and 221/223 which lose CO to give ions at *m/z* 188 and 177/179 and which further lose CO to give ions at *m/z* 160 and 149/151 respectively. The peaks corresponding to arylfuronitrile were not observed in these cases (Scheme 2).

Experimental

3-Substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles were prepared according to literature methods⁵. Arylfurfurals were obtained through Meerwein reaction⁶.

The mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol JMS D-300 spectrometer operating at 70 eV. Purity of the compounds were checked by tlc on silica gel plates using benzene : ethanol (2 : 1) solvent system and iodine as visualizing agent.

Substituted 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3) : To the Schiff base (**1**; 10 mmol) suspended in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), a solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (5 ml; 30%) was added with stirring for ~30 min, and the solution was set aside for 16 h. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallized from dimethylformamide-ethanol (2 : 1).

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